

SLR: Load Profiling Studies in Africa: The Gap on Energy Consumption in Developing Regions.

Initial search string:

“(TI=(modelling OR estimation OR comparison OR model OR demonstration OR prediction) AND TI=(electricity OR electricity demand OR load profile OR energy demand OR energy profile OR energy development) AND TI=(function OR household OR daily OR hourly OR high resolution OR interview OR data driven OR residential OR survey OR MGM OR MECM OR ARIMA))”.

Refined search string

“(TI=(review OR modelling OR estimation OR comparison OR model OR demonstration OR prediction) AND TI=(electricity OR electricity demand OR load profile OR energy demand OR energy profile OR energy development) AND TI=(function OR household OR daily OR hourly OR high resolution OR interview OR data driven OR residential OR survey OR time series OR ARIMA) AND TI=(agricultural OR rural OR non developed OR non-developed OR developing OR africa OR african OR ECOWAS OR algeria OR south africa OR nigeria OR morocco OR angola OR tanzania OR west african OR north africa OR central african OR eastern african OR ghana OR tunissia OR kenya OR cameroon OR egypt OR mali OR ECCAS OR EAC OR IGAD OR UMA OR SADC OR CEN-SAD))”.

Table A1: Number of studies directly associated to each African country

Number of studies	1	2	3	5
Countries	Benin, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Ivory Coast, Congo, Democratic Republic of Congo, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Gambia, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Sao Tome and Principe, Togo, Mauritania, Algeria, Kenya	Angola, Nigeria	Ghana	South Africa

Figure A1: General flow of load forecasting